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TOWARDS UNDERSTANDING AND MODELING IRREVERSIBLE BEHAVIOR OF WOVEN FABRICS UNDER LOADING-UNLOADING BENDING REGIMES

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Outline

- Introduction
 - Manufacturing outline
 - Misalignments
- Motivation
- Meso-Level Fabric Bending
 - Test Procedure
 - Modelling
 - Validations
 - Case Studies
- Conclusion

Aerospace Manufacturing Outline

Misalignments

What is waviness and wrinkling?

Fiber Misalignment

- Deviation from the nominal intended fiber direction specified in the design

Fiber waviness

- Refers to in-plane misalignment of tows

Wrinkling

- Refers to out-of-plane misalignment, i.e. occurring in the **through thickness** direction

Bloom, L. D., J. Wang, and K. D. Potter. "Damage progression and defect sensitivity: An experimental study of representative wrinkles in tension." *Composites Part B: Engineering* 45.1 (2013): 449-458.

Potter, K., et al. "Variability, fibre waviness and misalignment in the determination of the properties of composite materials and structures." *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 39.9 (2008): 1343-1354.

Tow buckling/waviness

Motivation

Forming of textile composites

Intra-ply shearing, inter-ply sliding, and out of plane bending
Limited to failure modes.

M. Komeili, PhD Thesis, UBC, 2014

Wrinkling

The most common defect.

Wrinkles' size and numbers

Depends on **Bending Rigidity**.

Low bending rigidity High bending rigidity

Boisse et al., 2014, Composites: Part A 67, pp. 111-122

Bending Stiffness

Inflatable woven fabric structures
Air beams
Hydraulic tubing systems

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Anti-plane Displacement
Limits Forming
Failure Modes

Bending Stiffness
Affects Wrinkling
Loading-Unloading
(Varying Bending Stiffness)
Hysteresis

Anti-plane Displacement
Limits Forming
Failure Modes

Peirce method developed in 1930s

- Based on **cantilever bending** of a textile specimen under its own weight
- Still used widely today
- Standards
- Bending has **linear** correlation with on curvature

Bilbao et al. 2009

- Non-elastic behaviour using history of strains
- Mechanical and optical part

Liang et al. 2014

- Added chamber
- Tested PEEK-carbon satin, PPS-Carbon satin prepregs

Soteropoulos et al. 2011

- Introduced vertical cantilever test
- Analyzed NC fabrics

Alshahrani 2017

- Loading rate-control using a linear actuator (up to 50 mm)
- Vertical cantilever test
- Temperature is monitored with infrared camera FLIR

Dangora et al. 2018

- Vertical cantilever method
- Radiant heater
- Cross-ply thermoplastic lamina

Bending apparatus 1974

- Loading cycle
- Stress relaxation
- creep

Kawabata bending test (KES-F2) 1980

- Obtains loading cycle
- Shows bending behaviour is **nonlinear**
- **Expensive**
- **Not well adopted for prepreg**

Martin et al. 1995

- V-shaped punch
- Thermal chamber
- Unidirectional thermoplastic composites

Bending Stiffness
Affects Wrinkling
Loading-Unloading
(Varying Bending Stiffness)
Hysteresis

Intra-yarn/Inter-yarn
Friction
Misalignment
Geometry
Undulation

Anti-plane Displacement
Limits Forming
Failure Modes

Bending Stiffness
 Effects Wrinkling
 Loading-Unloading
 (Varying Bending Stiffness)
 Hysteresis

Intra-yarn/Inter-yarn
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Anti-plane Displacement
 Limits Forming
 Failure Modes

Bending Experiments

Meso-Level Bending Experiments

5 Replicates
 Room Temperature
 2-yarn depth (1cm)
 3-yarn width (~1.5 cm)

Select material: Plain weave Glass/PP Twintex

Varying bending rigidity
 (slope of moment-curvature curve)

Energy dissipation
 through cyclic loadings

Friction between yarns
 Friction between fibers within yarns
 Numerous degree of freedom of fibers

Initial misalignment of fibers in each yarn

Significant **change** in fiber arrangement

How do these affect yarns behavior?

Conducting tensile tests to understand these effects

Meso-level bending simulation

Meso-Level Modeling

Thickness = 0.7 mm
 Yarn length = 5.0 mm
 Width of cross section = 1.0 mm

Detailed yarn geometry
 modeled directly in
 Abaqus

$$y = \frac{h}{2} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{s}\right) - 1 \right]$$

Modified function based on
 McBride & Chen "Unit-cell geometry in plain-weave fabrics During
 shear deformations", *Composites Science and Technology* 51(1997)
 345-351

Fixed

Joined points

Moving

Validation

Case I

Case II

Case III

		Case I	Case II	Case III
No. of Nodes		2714	10974	38822
Run-Time		8min 7s	25min 30s	177min 40s
Error (%) w.r.t. Experiment	t=0.8	7.64	11.04	10.91
	t=0.92	18.73	16.89	9.17
	t=1.00	25.62	7.30	7.56
Error (%) Compared to Case III	t=0.8	3.67	0.14	
	t=0.92	10.53	8.50	
	t=1.00	19.54	0.28	

Case Study: Unit Cell

Dry control condition

25% stiffer than control

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the effect of parameters under cyclic bending of the representative unit cell.

Factors	DOF	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	F	P-Value
Friction	2	0.23	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle	3	198.85	66.28	331.4	4.7115e-7
(Yarn) Material	1	1.52	1.52	7.60	0.03299
Friction× Bending Angle	6	1.20	0.20	1.0	0.5
Friction× Material	2	0.21	0.11	0.55	0.6035
Bending Angle× Material	3	1.03	0.34	1.70	0.2654
Error=Friction× Bending Angle× Material	6	1.17	0.20		
Total	23	204.21			

4 various angle of rotation (30°, 45°, 60°, 90°)
 3 different friction coefficients (0.1, 0.3, 0.6)
 2 different material properties (25% stiffer than dry fabric)

- Doubling the **angle of rotation (sharper forming)** almost triples the amount of moment.
- By increasing the **material stiffness** by 25%, max moment increases by ~33%.

Bending Stiffness
Affects Wrinkling
Loading-Unloading
(Varying Bending Stiffness)
Hysteresis

Intra-yarn/Inter-yarn
Friction
Misalignment
Geometry
Undulation

Macro-level bending

Forming of fabrics
Loading-unloading phase

Forming Parameters
Wrinkling

Anti-plane Displacement
Limits Forming
Failure Modes

Conclusion

- Bending rigidity nonlinearly **varies** through loading-unloading regimes.
- Bending rigidity highly affects the forming predictions, especially **wrinkling**.
- Current bending meso-model shows good accuracy with experiments.
- Implementing bending behavior into model **enhances** the accuracy of the forming predictions.

Thank you.